

SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORTATION, CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AND PATENT STRATEGY:

IS TESLA'S PATENT PLEDGE A WORK OF SOCIAL VALUE OR A MARKETING DECISION?

Dr Sadaf Shariat¹

Sadaf.shariat@southwales.ac.uk

University of South Wales, United Kingdom

Shahab GholizadehDastjerd²

SGholizadehdastjerd@cardiffmet.ac.uk

Cardiff Metropolitan University, United Kingdom

Abstract:

This research offers an interdisciplinary analysis of a dimension of Tesla's marketing strategy intricately linked to the company's unique innovation management and intellectual property protection. The primary objective of this study is to explore the use of patents in new technologies, assessing the extent to which automotive industry rely on intellectual property mechanisms as strategic tools for growth and marketing promotion. It is crucial to investigate whether an open innovation strategy, such as a patent pledge adopted by Tesla, would be considered an effective and intelligent approach to green marketing.

The genesis of this research stems from earlier studies in which the authors examined patent developments in technology markets and their impact on business growth, competitiveness, and Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives.³ The findings of that study prompted the authors to delve further into the application of Technological Social

¹ Corresponding author: Dr Sadaf Shariat, LLB, LLM, MBA (CSR), FHEA, PhD, Head of Intellectual Property Programme and Director of Law, Technology and Innovation at University of South Wales, United Kingdom.

² Shahab Gholizadehdastjerd, BA, MA (Technology Design), Research Assistant, Department of Technologies, Cardiff Metropolitan University, United Kingdom.

³ Shariat, S., & Gholizadehdastjerd, S. (2022a). Patent Developments in Technology Markets: Business Growth, Competitiveness and Corporate Social Responsibility. Paper presented at XXI International Congress on Public and Non-profit Marketing, Braga, Portugal.

Responsibility in selected cases of new and emerging technologies related to green technology solutions, green intellectual property, smart mobility, and sustainable transport.

^{4 5}

The results of prior studies conducted by the authors in the area of green technology, patent protection, and innovation management underscored the necessity for additional interdisciplinary research to connect the dots between green marketing, sustainable transport, and open innovation—particularly the patent pledge promoted by Tesla.

Keywords:

Open innovation; Sustainable transport; Technological Social Responsibility; Tesla Patent pledge; Green marketing

1. Introduction

The automotive industry is known as one of the major contributors to emissions. Car manufacturers, including companies involved in the advent of emerging technologies in

⁴ Shariat, S., & Gholizadehdastjerd, S. (2022). Technological Social Responsibility: The Power of Innovation Technology to Align Corporate and Societal Interests. Paper presented at the 9th International Conference on Social Responsibility, Ethics and Sustainable Business, Östersund, Sweden.

⁵ Shariat, S., & Gholizadehdastjerd, S. (2023). Technological Social Responsibility, Smart Cities, and Mobility: Making a Case for People with Disability. Paper presented at the 10th International Conference on Corporate Responsibility and Sustainability: Past, Present, Future, Bucharest, Romania, ICSR 2023.

the industry, aim to take steps to reduce their carbon emissions through various strategies.⁶ Tesla Motors, the U.S. electric vehicle manufacturer, serves as a notable example of a company striving to advance the manufacturing of alternative technologies with the aim of reducing greenhouse gas emissions. However, the company faces challenges associated with introducing affordable innovations for electric vehicles and meeting the growing demand, including high battery costs and performance competitiveness. Addressing these existing challenges is crucial to making investments in electric vehicles economically viable.⁷

With an ambitious vision statement, where Tesla portrays itself as 'the most compelling car company of the 21st century by driving the world's transition to electric vehicles,'⁸ the company highlights a serious ambition of leading other automobile manufacturers into the electric model future. Tesla places its priority in its mission statement as 'to accelerate the world's transition to sustainable energy,'⁹ indicating the company sincerely believes in promoting the transition to electric vehicles and sustainable energy. The company aims to distinguish itself from other players in the market by taking seemingly bold actions in this direction—some of which may raise serious questions for stakeholders.

A controversial decision made by the company is related to a 'patent pledge' announced by Elon Musk the CEO of Tesla, indicating the intention of the company to allow others to use of a number of existing IP properties of Tesla (provided that certain conditions are met).

*Tesla irrevocably pledges that it will not initiate a lawsuit against any party for infringing a Tesla Patent through activity relating to electric vehicles or related equipment for so long as such party is acting in good faith. Key terms of the Pledge are explained below.*¹⁰

The motivation of Tesla for making such a decision was allegedly to promote the 'open-source movement for the advancement of electric vehicle technology.'¹¹ This claim, however, may invite criticism and disagreement, supporting the notion that Tesla did not relinquish its portfolio of intellectual property rights freely, without any conditions or commercial expectations. Intellectual property rights bear significant value for corporations, and on certain occasions, these assets may hold greater value than the tangible

⁶ Kushwaha, G. S., & Sharma, V. (2015). Green initiatives: a step towards sustainable development and firm's performance in the automobile industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 121, 116.

⁷ McKinsey & Company. (2013). *The Road to 2020 and Beyond: What's Driving the Global Automotive Industry?* (pp. 1-24). Retrieved from: www.mckinsey.com.

⁸ Tesla. (2014). All Our Patent Are Belong To You. Retrieved from <https://www.tesla.com/blog/all-our-patent-are-belong-you>.

⁹ *ibid.*

¹⁰ *ibid.*

¹¹ *Ibid.*

assets of the company. Patents, in particular, signal the success and innovation of a company and the quality of the products/services it offers.¹²

Potential investors regard patents as invaluable indicators of future revenue streams, even in the absence of a high valuation of a company's tangible assets.¹³ The negative right associated with a patent provides a monopoly that prevents competitors or other corporations willing to use the technology from commercially exploiting the invention. Subsequently, other companies would require formal authorisation and payment of a licence to utilise the service. This decision by Tesla appears controversial from legal, technological, and business perspectives. One might question the value of such a strategy if it jeopardizes the interests of shareholders and commercial returns. While this decision may imply greater access to green technology with less fear of legal repercussions and reduced revenue from patent accounts, this research aims to examine various aspects of such a decision and analyse whether Tesla's patent pledge was genuinely a contribution of social value or a strategic marketing decision.

2. Case development

2.1 The Positive Image Cultivated for the Company in Addressing Climate Change

The environmentally conscious consumer holds a deep appreciation for Tesla's commitment to fostering eco-friendly transportation and combatting climate change. The implementation of sustainable practices and the formulation of policies aimed at enhancing energy efficiency resonate positively with broader society. Notably, investments in green technologies or initiatives to promote the sector, even at the expense of potential profit loss—illustrated by Tesla's willingness to permit the use of its patents—command recognition and respect within the market, ultimately elevating the brand image.

Tesla's corporate culture not only nurtures innovation internally but also endeavors to propagate innovative practices within the sector through collaborations with other market players. The patent pledge has the potential to enhance public admiration for the company, as individuals recognise Tesla's engagement in socially responsible activities and

¹² Garavito Hernández, Y., & Rueda Galvis, J. F. (2021). Innovation and patents as a business success factor. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Science*, 26(51), 143-159. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEFAS-09-2019-0218>

¹³ Andrews, D., & de Serres, A. (2012). *Intangible Assets, Resource Allocation and Growth: A Framework for Analysis* (OECD Economics Department Working Papers No. 989). OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5k92s63w14wb-en>.

environmentally sustainable practices, thereby promoting access to cutting-edge technologies for car manufacturers.

2.2 Green Marketing Strategy

Tesla's patent pledge could also be considered a form of green marketing. The open-source strategy adopted by Tesla aims to stimulate the development and widespread adoption of electric vehicles throughout the automotive industry, thereby fostering environmental sustainability and the integration of eco-friendly vehicles into the transportation system.¹⁴

As previously discussed, the company's innovation and patent policy have cultivated a positive image, portraying Tesla as a corporation deeply committed to environmental responsibility. This commitment extends beyond the production of eco-friendly electric cars, as Tesla actively strives to promote the adoption of sustainable technologies within the automotive manufacturing sector. Moreover, Tesla seeks to engender increased innovation and collaboration within the electric vehicle sector, an approach that unequivocally supports the expansion of the green technology market. Tesla underscores the company's commitment to advancing overarching goals, including the reduction of carbon emissions and the combatting of climate change. This might be achievable using the company's electric vehicle technologies, typically protected by various Tesla patents.

Beyond considerations of brand image and consumer perception, as explored in earlier sections, Tesla's willingness to share selected patented technologies could potentially exert influence on the market and competitors. This influence may pave the way for the adoption of similar green practices in the future, effectively altering market dynamics and contributing to a more sustainable automotive industry. While the primary intention behind the patent pledge appears to be Tesla's genuine intent to propel the adoption of electric vehicles and address environmental challenges, partially attributed to intellectual property barriers, the strategy also aligns with the principles of green marketing. It holds the potential to promote sustainability, collaboration, and a positive environmental impact.

2.3 Protecting Shareholders' Interests

The Condition of Acting in 'Good Faith' in Tesla's Patent Pledge

¹⁴ Tesla. (2014). All Our Patent Are Belong To You. Retrieved from <https://www.tesla.com/blog/all-our-patent-are-belong-you>.

In terms of the legal effect of Tesla's patent pledge, one may begin to examine the language of the pledge, with particular reference to the concept of 'good faith' as stated in the following statement:

The Pledge, which is irrevocable and legally binding on Tesla and its successors, is a "standstill," meaning that it is a forbearance of enforcement of Tesla's remedies against any party for claims of infringement for so long as such party is acting in good faith.¹⁵

The above statement emphasises the importance of 'good faith' in the patent pledge. This emphasis is further detailed with additional caveats specifying that the company or its affiliated companies, when acting in 'good faith,' must not have ever engaged in certain activities. Tesla provides the following list to clarify what actions a company acting in good faith must not have taken:

- *asserted, helped others assert or had a financial stake in any assertion of (i) any patent or other intellectual property right against Tesla or (ii) any patent right against a third party for its use of technologies relating to electric vehicles or related equipment;*
- *challenged, helped others challenge, or had a financial stake in any challenge to any Tesla patent; or*
- *marketed or sold any knock-off product (e.g., a product created by imitating or copying the design or appearance of a Tesla product or which suggests an association with or endorsement by Tesla) or provided any material assistance to another party doing so.¹⁶*

The statement indicates that the patent pledge is not freely available to all. If a company does not meet the 'good faith' requirements set by Tesla, they would not be able to benefit from the opportunity provided. Although Tesla aims to promote an open-source IP strategy and a transition toward sustainable electrical mobility, the example of Tesla and its strategy demonstrates how a company's strategic utilization of IP can protect the business model of the company against market competitors, with the ultimate goal of creating a societal impact.¹⁷

From a financial standpoint, one might argue that while the patent pledge creates a positive impression of an altruistic strategy, it may not necessarily result in significant expenditure on Tesla's part. The extensive list of qualifying requirements outlined in the patent pledge significantly limits opportunities, primarily favouring Tesla. The definition of "good faith,"

¹⁵ *ibid.*

¹⁶ *ibid.*

¹⁷ Sternkopf, J., Tietze, F., Eppinger, E., & Vimalnath, P. (2016). Open IP strategies for enabling sustainability transitions. Centre for Technology Management Working Paper Series, ISSN 2058-8887.

as discussed earlier, encompasses entities that have refrained from suing Tesla for IP infringement (beyond Tesla patents alone) or have not been involved in *challenging, aiding others in challenging, or having a financial stake in any challenge to any Tesla patent*.¹⁸ Despite Tesla presenting this as legally binding, questions arise regarding its enforceability, given that it is not a formal contract and might not be legally binding.¹⁹ Tesla provides clarification on the terms of the pledge as follows:

*In order for Tesla to preserve its ability to enforce the Tesla Patents against any party not acting in good faith, **the Pledge is not a waiver of any patent claims** (including claims for damages for past acts of infringement) and is **not a license, covenant not to sue, or authorization to engage in patented activities or a limitation on remedies, damages or claims**. Except as expressly stated in the Pledge, **no rights shall be deemed granted, waived or received by implication, exhaustion, estoppel or otherwise**. Finally, **the Pledge is not an indication of the value of an arms-length, negotiated license or a reasonable royalty**.²⁰*

As evident from the additional notes provided by Tesla, the company has successfully protected its patents without overly extending benefits. Simultaneously, they affirm that “*as long as someone uses our patents for electric vehicles and doesn’t do bad things, such as knocking off our products or using our patents and then suing us for intellectual property infringement, they should have no fear of Tesla asserting its patents against them*”.²¹ While the statement above aims to clarify issues regarding the patent pledge, criticism persists that companies remain in an uncertain position regarding the precise interpretation of the pledge, and signing it may give rise to complications.²²

In defining ‘good faith’, references have been made to ‘looking for common sense and fairness’²³, suggesting that those uncertain about the implications or concerned about the risks would have the option to enter into simple agreements with Tesla.²⁴ There is an argument in Contract Law-related literature that an intellectual property license may be claimed not to be a contractual right, potentially resulting in the transformation of contractual provisions into intellectual property provisions.²⁵ The absence of clarity in this

¹⁸ Tesla. (2014). Additional Resources: Patent List. Retrieved from <https://www.tesla.com/legal/additional-resources#patent-list>.

¹⁹ Hill, B. M. (2016). Powering Intellectual Property Sharing: How to Make Tesla's Patent Pledge Effective. *Journal of Intellectual Property Law*, 24, 199-200.

²⁰ Tesla. (2014). Additional Resources: Patent List. Retrieved from <https://www.tesla.com/legal/additional-resources#patent-list>.

²¹ *ibid.*

²² Hill, B. M. (2016). Powering Intellectual Property Sharing: How to Make Tesla's Patent Pledge Effective. *Journal of Intellectual Property Law*, 24, 199-200.

²³ *ibid.*

²⁴ *ibid.*

²⁵ Hill, 209-210.

context and the uncertainties raised might result in fewer companies availing themselves of the opportunity provided by Tesla. However, the significant public impact resulting from the patent pledge announcement would persist. It is also conceivable that a company, while accepting Tesla's offer, could make a mistake that potentially subjects the company to future litigation in a dispute with Tesla.

2.4 Other Benefits for Tesla

A reduction in advertising costs, stemming from an improved positive reputation for the company, aligns seamlessly with Tesla's zero expenditure on advertising.²⁶ Therefore, any potential losses resulting from Tesla's decision not to pursue patent infringement lawsuits could be assessed in comparison to standard expenditures for an advertising budget. Additionally, the company would project a more positive image of social responsibility by making a prudent decision regarding the protection of its patents.

Intellectual property law plays a crucial role in balancing private and public interests. On the one hand, protecting inventors stands as a critical necessity for nurturing innovation and securing investments in Research and Development. Simultaneously, it is imperative to avoid excessively stringent protective measures, as such rigidity may impede the dissemination of new ideas, consequently adversely affecting both social interests and economic growth.²⁷ Furthermore, with regard to company size, smaller enterprises are often perceived as more likely than their larger counterparts to engender innovations that bear social advantage.²⁸ The restrictive access to essential technologies, typically patented by larger companies, holds the potential to impede societal progress.

The open IP approach adopted by Tesla and other responsible technology firms promotes a system of increased cross-licensing, free and fair use of patents, and greater access to shared research and development. Although open-source technology sharing is not very common, there are circumstances in which companies have availed their intellectual property rights for the greater societal benefits. A similarly positive strategy concerning a company's IP assets is the use of 'patent pools,' which provides greater access to patented

²⁶ Koetsier, J. (2019, May 6). Tesla Spends Zero On Ads. Here's Where BMW, Toyota, Ford, and Porsche Spend Digital Ad Dollars. *Forbes*. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/johnkoetsier/2019/05/06/tesla-spends-zero-on-ads-heres-where-bmw-toyota-ford-and-porsche-spend-digital-ad-dollars/?sh=6c18060111d4>

²⁷ Gould, D. M., & Gruben, D. (1996). The Role of Intellectual Property Rights in Economic Growth. *Journal of Development Economics*, 48(2), 323-350.

²⁸ Teece, D. J. (1986). Profiting from Technological Innovation: Implications for Integration, Collaboration, Licensing and Public Policy. *Research Policy*, 15(6), 285-305

technologies.²⁹ Patent pooling, as a more formalised multilateral agreement, occurs between a group of companies that mutually share their intellectual property rights. It is noteworthy that a patent pooling system would differ from a strategy akin to Tesla's patent pledge. Patent pooling may not necessarily provide benefits for many companies in the market, and concerns have been raised regarding competition law issues. Specifically, these concerns arise in circumstances where intellectual property rights are shared within a group of companies that already collectively hold a large market share.³⁰

3. Questions/issues for discussion

Considering the issues raised in the development of the case in section 2, there are three key questions to address in this section.

3.1 Question 1: Can Tesla's patent pledge be considered an effective marketing mechanism to boost the sales of Tesla's patented innovations?

The first question is whether Tesla's patent pledge could be deemed a responsible decision to enhance the brand image in the market. Additionally, did Tesla effectively protect the interests of shareholders while acting responsibly toward society and the environment? Overall, can Tesla's patent pledge be considered an effective marketing mechanism to boost the sales of Tesla's patented innovations?

In addition to the discussions in section 2.5, it is crucial to delve into the issue concerning the availability of future protection for Tesla in the event of illegally infringing patents from other companies. The 'free will' condition set in Tesla's patent pledge could also have other positive implications for Tesla. The terms in the patent pledge would enable Tesla to potentially bypass any claims made by other companies in a situation where Tesla is allegedly illegally infringing on their patents. The reluctance of other companies to take action against Tesla could be attributed to the fact that their company may be in possession of Tesla's IP.

Rogan makes a compelling statement regarding companies utilising Tesla's technology, asserting that "*using Tesla's technology would essentially render any other company's intellectual property rights redundant.*"³¹ In contrast, Tesla stands to benefit from this arrangement as the company will have the right to incorporate any improvements made to

²⁹ Grzegorzcyk, T. (2020). Managing Intellectual Property: Strategies for Patent Holders. The Journal of High Technology Management Research, 31(1), 100374.

³⁰ WIPO. (2014). Patent Pools and Antitrust – A Comparative Analysis.

³¹ Rogan, J. (2020). "Does Tesla's open source patent philosophy mean they are free to use?" Venner Shipley. Retrieved from <https://www.vennershipley.co.uk/news/blog/does-teslas-open-source-patent-philosophy-mean-they-are-free-to-use/>. Accessed November 10, 2023.

its technology by another party. Additionally, Tesla anticipates that other companies using its patents refrain from litigating against Tesla or imposing licensing fees when Tesla incorporates their similarly valued technology.³²

Overall, it seems that while Tesla has cultivated a positive image as a responsible business, the strategy has not imposed significant burdens. The legal framework of the pledge, including elements like the 'good faith' condition, justifies and makes the strategy reasonable for shareholders. It ensures that the company will not be disadvantaged by actions taken regarding its selected patents. Tesla is shielded by the patent pledge in a way that, if another company benefits from Tesla's patented technology and patents the result, preventing Tesla from using the technology, then Tesla will have the option to sue the competitor for infringement. This claim would be based on the assertion that the company has not satisfied the requirements of 'good faith' as explained in the terms of the patent pledge.³³ Companies choosing to accept Tesla's offer are recommended to use a patent Creative Commons license to afford some degree of control.^{34 35}

Furthermore, the qualifying requirements in defining 'good faith' protect Tesla's interests in circumstances where another company is selling 'knock-off products,' essentially marketing items produced using Tesla's patents as if they were Tesla products.³⁶ It serves as further evidence for shareholders that the company places a significance on business interests, mirroring the importance attributed to corporate values and social responsibility. Moreover, Tesla has anticipated additional protection for the company in its dealings with Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs). The implication of the patent pledge for an automotive OEM, upon signing the patent, grants Tesla the right to use technology within the scope of the OEM's patent portfolio. In cases where an automotive OEM entity does

³² Hill, B. M. (2016). Powering Intellectual Property Sharing: How to Make Tesla's Patent Pledge Effective. *Journal of Intellectual Property Law*, 24, 199-200.

³³ Lucek, N. W. (2014, July 11). "Take Off Every Zig: The Risk in Tesla's 'All Our Patent Are Belong to You' Message." *Clean and Green Law*.

³⁴ Hill, B. M. (2016). Powering Intellectual Property Sharing: How to Make Tesla's Patent Pledge Effective. *Journal of Intellectual Property Law*, 24, 199-200.

³⁵ Furthermore, the doctrine of equitable estoppel has been suggested as a potential legal protection for companies interested in considering Tesla's offer. The doctrine of equitable estoppel is assessed using a three-part test where the defendant must prove that: "1) the patentee, through misleading conduct, leads the alleged infringer to reasonably infer that the patentee does not intend to enforce its patent against the alleged infringer; 2) the alleged infringer relies on that conduct, and 3) due to its reliance, the alleged infringer will be materially prejudiced if the patentee is allowed to proceed with its claim". For further discussion, refer to Hill (2016, p.11), citing *Ecolab, Inc.*, 264 F.3d at 1371, which, in turn, cites *Scholle Corp. v. Blackhawk Molding Co.*, 133 F.3d 1469, 1473 (Fed. Cir. 1998)

³⁶ Tesla. (2014). Additional Resources: Patent Pledge. Retrieved from <https://www.tesla.com/legal/additional-resources#patent-list>.

not align with the patent pledge, Tesla maintains the option to enforce its patents against the automotive OEM.³⁷

Overall, while Tesla's patent pledge extends benefits to the public, it also serves to protect the company. As expressed by Hill³⁸, "*Tesla opening up their patents is good for both the company and the public by allowing others to use and transform the technology*³⁹, and *recognizing the need for communal innovation allows for a better realization of the future value when dealing with a high tech sector of a traditional good.*"⁴⁰

3.2 Question 2: Are Tesla's Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives strategically aligned with the company's core values, particularly concerning innovation management strategy (in relation to electric vehicle patents discussed in this article)?

The second question focuses on the issues related to the alignment of social responsibility with the core values of the company.

Tesla's strategy to advancement of electric vehicle technology and promoting sustainable transport is well aligned the company's CSR initiatives and also core values. Tesla's emphasises on the core values of "doing the best, taking risks, respect, constant learning, and environmental consciousness."⁴¹ The company's innovation management strategy (in relation to patents) seems in line with the company's core values. It also gives the impression to the market and customers that the company genuinely integrates CSR initiatives/ socially responsible practices into its operation which also reflects the commitment of the company core values. Tesla recognises and aims to promote 'environmental consciousness'⁴² and sustainability, it is therefore expected of the company

³⁷ "Why Tesla's Open Source Patent Strategy Reinforces the Importance of Patenting." StartupNation. Retrieved from <https://startupnation.com/manage-your-business/teslas-open-source-patent-strategy/>.

³⁸ Hill, B. M. (2016). Powering Intellectual Property Sharing: How to Make Tesla's Patent Pledge Effective. *Journal of Intellectual Property Law*, 24, p. 198

³⁹ Bailey, J. A. (2014). AIA: The Building Block of Communal Innovation. *Connecticut Public Interest Law Journal*, 13, 325-348.

⁴⁰ Bar-Gill, O., & Parchomovsky, G. (2003). The Value of Giving Away Secrets. *Virginia Law Review*, 89, p. 198.

⁴¹ Tesla. (2023). Tesla Mission and Vision Statement Analysis. Retrieved from <https://mission-statement.com/tesla/#Core Values>

⁴² Tesla. (2023). Tesla Environmental Impact. Retrieved from <https://www.tesla.com/environmental-impact>.

to implement CSR initiatives – including the way in which the company manages its innovation and portfolio of intellectual property- which protects environment and promotes access to green eco- friendly technology.

The corporate strategy concerning open-source patents, designed to facilitate access to Tesla's innovation system, aligns seamlessly with the company's core values. This approach, coupled with a commitment to open and transparent communication, fosters trust. Tesla openly shares its values, achievements, and challenges, thereby cultivating a positive image and bolstering its reputation among customers and stakeholders. The robust connection between Corporate Social Responsibility initiatives and core values contributes significantly to the brand image and garners admiration from the public. The alignment of CSR initiatives, core values, and overall corporate strategy and practices positions Tesla advantageously to exert a positive impact on the electric vehicle industry and society while adhering to its foundational principles.

As any other decisions that companies make, the patent strategy and generally the waiver of any IP portfolio must be justified so to determine the extent of any social and economic benefit which arise as a result of a given strategy adopted. In a patent context, the countries with a relatively weak economy that are net importers of patented technologies would be subject of unavoidable cost which has been caused by enforcement of patent monopolies.⁴³ Challenges of this nature may impede the diffusion of innovation,⁴⁴ potentially causing a slowdown significant enough to result in delays for developing nations in establishing their domestic innovation capacity, especially when patent protections are strengthened. This constrain primarily affects the 'imitation phase,' wherein local technical knowledge emerges through the process of replicating new products. Consequently, this restriction is likely to contribute to the exacerbation of existing international inequalities.

It is, however, questionable whether other companies would choose a completely open model of patent-sharing. As this is a rare choice in the market, there is limited evidence to analyse the actual economic impact of such a decision on a company. Interestingly, evidence from other sectors, including environmental innovation and healthcare technologies, demonstrates that there is no serious willingness to accept the commercial

⁴³Hoekman, B. M., Maskus, K. E., & Saggi, K. (2004). Transfer of technology to developing countries: unilateral and multilateral policy options. World Bank Policy Research Working Paper No. 3332, 3.

⁴⁴ Strobel, C. (2013). Wind Power and Patent Law: How the Enforcement of Wind Technology Patents May Lead to Restricted Implementation in the US, and Necessary Solutions. *Journal of Environmental and Sustainability Law*, 19, 501.

disadvantages of an open-source IP strategy, even on occasions where public interest is seriously at stake. The case of the Covid vaccine, although it was believed that "global inequity would lead to many more deaths," the argument still did not convince shareholders of vaccine manufacturing companies. The idea of Moderna undertaking a feasibility study into transferring intellectual property and technical know-how to manufacturers in low- and middle-income countries was supported by only 24% of shareholders. In Pfizer, 27% of shareholders were in favour of a similar course of action, and Johnson and Johnson, although not disclosing a number, had the proposal failed among shareholders.⁴⁵ Open-source knowledge sharing is a practice seen in the software business, but there is no evidence of its popularity among other sectors. That said, there have been academic comments regarding the potential benefits of such a system to avoid the creation of overlapping and mutually problematic 'patent thickets.'⁴⁶ Within the context of environmental inventions, it is interesting that the open-source strategy was not used in the case of any inventions featured in the Environmental European Inventor Awards (EIA) between 2006 and 2020.⁴⁷

3.3 Question 3: How is Tesla's decision reinforcing the importance of a proper patent strategy in both benefiting from the market and offering benefits to the market simultaneously?

The choice of open-source patent strategy adopted by Tesla in this instance not only emphasises the company's value system and environmental strategy but goes well beyond that, reinforcing the importance of a right intellectual property strategy in general and a patent strategy in particular. While the right strategy protects the innovation and maintains a competitive advantage, this 'right' does not always equate to the 'strictest.' In this case, Tesla makes the right choice, which will benefit the market, environment, and the wider stakeholder in a holistic view. However, this does not necessarily mean that the company has made a decision against the interests of shareholders.

Given the intense competition in the market, market penetration poses a significant challenge for start-up companies, especially in the context of the considerable investment required for establishing a new car manufacturing business. In the case of electric vehicles,

⁴⁵ Josephs, J. (2022, April 29). Investors lose vote to share Covid vaccine know-how. BBC News. Retrieved from <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/business-61262065>

⁴⁶ Lerner, J., & Tirole, J. (2005). The Economics of Technology Sharing: Open Source and Beyond. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 19(2), 99-116.

⁴⁷ Vimalnath, P., Tietze, F., Prifti, V., & Akriti, J. (2020). IP Strategies for Green Innovations – An Analysis of European Inventor Awards. Centre for Technology Management Working Paper Series, 17.

a new company faces the additional need to invest in infrastructure facilities, such as battery charging stations and battery replacement services, to ensure the smooth operation of the electric vehicle network.⁴⁸ Consequently, a collaborative approach involving partnerships with other manufacturers in the same industry, aimed at sharing knowledge and potentially certain facilities, becomes an attractive option for many companies.⁴⁹ Tesla has effectively implemented such a strategy by fostering cooperation with other companies in the sector. The company has developed a strategic alliance network encompassing suppliers, research and development, and other crucial aspects, positioning itself to derive multiple benefits across various aspects of its business.

It is, therefore, questionable whether Tesla's patent pledge has emerged merely on an altruistic basis. Tesla alone would not be able to effect a drastic change in the world of the electric vehicle market. The company emphasises the importance of the need for accelerated innovation within the electric vehicle manufacturing industry and that the open innovation strategy adopted by the company will not affect their 'innovative progress' in the market, as the company will not be able to manufacture electric cars on their own at a sufficient rate to solve environmental issues such as a carbon crisis. Only lower than 1% of total vehicle sale was formed by alternative fuel vehicle sales at top automobile manufacturers.⁵⁰ The strategy of making their patents available to other companies provides a greater chance for those companies to transition to electric vehicle engines. The information disclosed in earlier patents will be an integral part of future emerging technologies, specifically in areas such as electric vehicles. Tesla's electric vehicles occupy the higher range of the market, making it challenging for competitors or smaller companies in the market to innovate in a manner that results in an entirely distinct competitive system.⁵¹ Tesla's strategic planning means that the company holds a wealth of patent value, and they assess and develop the right patent strategy from time to time to align with business goals and market dynamics.

⁴⁸ On this matter, refer to the comments by Eric Lane from Thomas Jefferson School of Law, accessible at [<https://greenpatentblog.com/2014/06/14/elon-musk-launches-the-tesla-patent-commons/>] “Ultimately, the impact of Musk's decision may turn on to what extent other such players will be motivated to invest in manufacturing vehicles, batteries, etc. using Tesla's patented and patent pending technology with the obvious upside being the proven innovation that technology brings and the down side being no exclusivity, instead of investing in their own R&D and patent protection where the upside may be exclusivity and the down side may be inferior or unproven technologies.”

⁴⁹ Bhargava, H., Boehm, J., & Parker, G. G. (2021, January 27). How Tesla's Charging Stations Left Other Manufacturers in the Dust. Harvard Business Review. Retrieved from <https://hbr.org/2021/01/how-teslas-charging-stations-left-other-manufacturers-in-the-dust>

⁵⁰ Tesla. (2014). All Our Patent Are Belong To You. Retrieved November 20, 2023, from <https://www.tesla.com/blog/all-our-patent-are-belong-you>

⁵¹ Hill, B. M. (2016). Powering Intellectual Property Sharing: How to Make Tesla's Patent Pledge Effective. *Journal of Intellectual Property Law*, 24, 199-200.

4. Conclusion

Patents are designed to encourage innovative activities by providing financial incentives in exchange for the disclosure and dissemination of information related to novel technologies. It is also argued that a company's possession of patents promotes future investment by external entities and assists the company in recovering the costs associated with the invention, including research and development (R&D) expenses. By incentivising innovation, a strong net positive effect is created, contributing to both economic and societal benefits. This implies that a company's innovation plays a pivotal role in fostering economic growth.⁵² Tesla decided not to initiate any patent litigation against a company that uses Tesla-patented technology, as long as it satisfies the requirements of 'good faith' outlined in the pledge. The ultimate goal of this strategy was to pave the way for widespread manufacturing and adoption of electric cars. In this research, the authors examined a number of costs and benefits conceivable for the company. Although Tesla manoeuvred towards the wider societal benefits of such a strategy and benefited from the positive image and enhanced brand reputation⁵³. created through these decisions, the benefits of the strategy for Tesla seemingly outweigh the costs.^{54 55} These benefits are protected through careful legal drafting of the pledge, providing a good opportunity for Tesla in the future, particularly in cases where Tesla could potentially be infringing on a company's patented technology. The research also emphasises that acting as good corporate citizens in the transport sector, although it may, in certain circumstances, lead to less profit (e.g., through reduced licensing, as in the case of Volvo seat belts)⁵⁶, would generate greater societal benefits. This, in turn, may further improve the brand reputation.

While authors observed a good range of protected benefits for Tesla in this case, such decisions in relation to patents must be made with caution as there might be an existential risk as can be seen in cases like IBM for the company in offering such mutual co-operation.

⁵² Benhabib, J., Perla, J., & Tonetti, C. (2014). Catch-up and fall-back through innovation and imitation. *Journal of Economic Growth*, 19(1), 1.

⁵³ IP Osgoode. (2021, April 14). Tesla's Patent Pledge: An altruistic act or a stroke of marketing genius? Retrieved April 2, 2023, from <https://www.iposgoode.ca/2020/04/teslas-patent-pledge-an-altruistic-act-or-a-stroke-of-marketing-genius/>

⁵⁴ Rojas, F. (2020, December 10). Eight Digital Marketing Lessons We Can Learn From Tesla. *Forbes*. Retrieved May 2, 2022, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbesagencycouncil/2020/12/10/eight-digital-marketing-lessons-we-can-learn-from-tesla/>

⁵⁵ IP Osgoode. (2021, April 14). Tesla's Patent Pledge: An altruistic act or a stroke of marketing genius? Retrieved April 2, 2023, from <https://www.iposgoode.ca/2020/04/teslas-patent-pledge-an-altruistic-act-or-a-stroke-of-marketing-genius/>

⁵⁶ J Benhabib, J Perla and C Tonetti, 'Catch-up and fall-back through innovation and imitation' (2014) 19(1) *Journal of Economic Growth*, 1

⁵⁷. In weighing the company's obligations towards shareholders and the broader societal benefits, Tesla or any other corporation on the verge of a decision similar to Tesla must take into account complex moral, environmental, and economic questions. The robust legal safeguards in place to protect Tesla's interests in the future help address concerns about unfettered altruism from a company director. Such concerns, if unmanaged, has the potential to subvert the intended function of the free market and may be construed as a neglect of their responsibilities to shareholders. While compliance with shareholder primacy is crucial, it may place decision-makers in a company in a situation where a diverse range of concerns over the corporation's social accountability remain unanswered. Tesla has effectively managed to justify the decision, which may seem purely altruistic at first glance, to shareholders through various actions taken in support of the company, most importantly the legal drafting of the patent pledge.

Bibliographic References

Andrews, D., & de Serres, A. (2012). Intangible Assets, Resource Allocation and Growth: A Framework for Analysis (OECD Economics Department Working Papers No. 989). OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5k92s63w14wb-en>.

Bailey, J. A. (2014). AIA: The Building Block of Communal Innovation. Connecticut Public Interest Law Journal, 13, 325-348.

⁵⁷ J Cortada and S Cherry, 'IBM's Fall From World Dominance', IEEE Spectrum podcast 11 August 2021.

- Bar-Gill, O., & Parchomovsky, G. (2003). The Value of Giving Away Secrets. *Virginia Law Review*, 89, p. 198.
- Benhabib, J., Perla, J., & Tonetti, C. (2014). Catch-up and fall-back through innovation and imitation. *Journal of Economic Growth*, 19(1), 1.
- Bhargava, H., Boehm, J., & Parker, G. G. (2021, January 27). How Tesla's Charging Stations Left Other Manufacturers in the Dust. *Harvard Business Review*. Retrieved from <https://hbr.org/2021/01/how-teslas-charging-stations-left-other-manufacturers-in-the-dust>
- Garavito Hernández, Y., & Rueda Galvis, J. F. (2021). Innovation and patents as a business success factor. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Science*, 26(51), 143-159. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEFAS-09-2019-0218>
- Gould, D. M., & Gruben, D. (1996). The Role of Intellectual Property Rights in Economic Growth. *Journal of Development Economics*, 48(2), 323-350.
- Grzegorzczak, T. (2020). Managing Intellectual Property: Strategies for Patent Holders. *The Journal of High Technology Management Research*, 31(1), 100374.
- Hill, B. M. (2016). Powering Intellectual Property Sharing: How to Make Tesla's Patent Pledge Effective. *Journal of Intellectual Property Law*, 24, 199-200.
- Hoekman, B. M., Maskus, K. E., & Saggi, K. (2004). Transfer of technology to developing countries: unilateral and multilateral policy options. *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper No. 3332*, 3.
- IP Osgoode. (2021, April 14). Tesla's Patent Pledge: An altruistic act or a stroke of marketing genius? Retrieved April 2, 2023, from <https://www.iposgoode.ca/2020/04/teslas-patent-pledge-an-altruistic-act-or-a-stroke-of-marketing-genius/>
- Josephs, J. (2022, April 29). Investors lose vote to share Covid vaccine know-how. *BBC News*. Retrieved from <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/business-61262065>
- Koetsier, J. (2019, May 6). Tesla Spends Zero On Ads. Here's Where BMW, Toyota, Ford, and Porsche Spend Digital Ad Dollars. *Forbes*. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/johnkoetsier/2019/05/06/tesla-spends-zero-on-ads-heres-where-bmw-toyota-ford-and-porsche-spend-digital-ad-dollars/?sh=6c18060111d4>
- Kushwaha, G. S., & Sharma, V. (2015). Green initiatives: a step towards sustainable development and firm's performance in the automobile industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 121, 116.
- Lerner, J., & Tirole, J. (2005). The Economics of Technology Sharing: Open Source and Beyond. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 19(2), 99-116.
- Lucek, N. W. (2014, July 11). "Take Off Every Zig: The Risk in Tesla's 'All Our Patent Are Belong to You' Message." *Clean and Green Law*.
- McKinsey & Company. (2013). *The Road to 2020 and Beyond: What's Driving the Global Automotive Industry?* (pp. 1-24). Retrieved from: www.mckinsey.com.
- Rogan, J. (2020). "Does Tesla's open source patent philosophy mean they are free to use?" *Venner Shipley*. Retrieved from <https://www.vennershipley.co.uk/news/blog/does-teslas->

[open-source-patent-philosophy-mean-they-are-free-to-use/](#). Accessed November 10, 2023.

Rojas, F. (2020, December 10). Eight Digital Marketing Lessons We Can Learn From Tesla. *Forbes*. Retrieved May 2, 2022, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbesagencycouncil/2020/12/10/eight-digital-marketing-lessons-we-can-learn-from-tesla/>

Shariat, S., & Gholizadehdastjerd, S. (2022a). Patent Developments in Technology Markets: Business Growth, Competitiveness and Corporate Social Responsibility. Paper presented at XXI International Congress on Public and Non-profit Marketing, Braga, Portugal.

Shariat, S., & Gholizadehdastjerd, S. (2022b). Technological Social Responsibility: The Power of Innovation Technology to Align Corporate and Societal Interests. Paper presented at the 9th International Conference on Social Responsibility, Ethics and Sustainable Business, Östersund, Sweden.

Shariat, S., & Gholizadehdastjerd, S. (2023). Technological Social Responsibility, Smart Cities, and Mobility: Making a Case for People with Disability. Paper presented at the 10th International Conference on Corporate Responsibility and Sustainability: Past, Present, Future, Bucharest, Romania, ICSR 2023.

Strobel, C. (2013). Wind Power and Patent Law: How the Enforcement of Wind Technology Patents May Lead to Restricted Implementation in the US, and Necessary Solutions. *Journal of Environmental and Sustainability Law*, 19, 501.

Teece, D. J. (1986). Profiting from Technological Innovation: Implications for Integration, Collaboration, Licensing and Public Policy. *Research Policy*, 15(6), 285-305.

Tesla. (2014). Additional Resources: Patent List. Retrieved from <https://www.tesla.com/legal/additional-resources#patent-list>.

Tesla. (2014). All Our Patent Are Belong To You. Retrieved from <https://www.tesla.com/blog/all-our-patent-are-belong-you>.

Tesla. (2023). Tesla Environmental Impact. Retrieved from <https://www.tesla.com/environmental-impact>.

Tesla. (2023). Tesla Mission and Vision Statement Analysis. Retrieved from https://mission-statement.com/tesla/#Core_Values

Vimalnath, P., Tietze, F., Prifti, V., & Akriti, J. (2020). IP Strategies for Green Innovations – An Analysis of European Inventor Awards. Centre for Technology Management Working Paper Series, 17.

"Why Tesla's Open Source Patent Strategy Reinforces the Importance of Patenting." StartupNation. Retrieved from <https://startupnation.com/manage-your-business/teslas-open-source-patent-strategy/>.

WIPO. (2014). Patent Pools and Antitrust – A Comparative Analysis. Retrieved from [Working Title: Patent Pools \(wipo.int\)](#)